

AI-based solutions in endoscopy image processing: robustness and certification

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Abstract: The artificial intelligence (AI) can efficiently analyze the image data of endoscopy videos; therefore, they can be utilized in the medical application such as surgical organization, diagnostics and therapy. The approval of commercial use of such AI systems is required, as the quality and potential risk of such systems need to be investigated. In this project, two aspects of AI systems in medical application were considered, on the one side the testing of AI safety and reliability, on the other side the developing of a verifiable AI system for health workers.

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I. Introduction

The AI model has many degrees of freedom and complex non-linear form. Generally, there is a risk that a slight modification in the input space would lead to unexpected and potentially dangerous behavior. Therefore, ensuring the robustness of the system is essential for any use in the medical domain. Endoscopic procedures have been considered a case study in this project. Mainly, the convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been employed for analyzing endoscopy images, e.g., recognizing surgical tools used in the endoscopic procedures. Using this example of identifying surgical tools in endoscopic images, the robustness and certification of AI-based methods have been studied in this project.

I.I. AI Robustness

The robustness of a CNN model includes two aspects which are the robustness to data from unseen sources, i.e., the generalizability, and the robustness to slightly modified adversaries. The adversary can be found by simply flip an input image [1], or linear interpolate two different images [2], and the CNN classification performance influenced by these input modifications. There are more complex methods such as use the loss gradient to craft imperceptible perturbations [3]. In this case, a step adaptive iterative fast gradient sign method was proposed. This method can generate less perturbations to fool a well-trained CNN [4,5].

In this project, two robustness improvement methods were introduced which are adding an additional loss function to help the CNN in feature space separation [6], and adversarial training with the borderline adversaries.

I.II. AI Certification

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) aims to make the operations of CNNs more interpretable by highlighting parts of an input image that contribute to a particular classification. This can help users, such as AI developers or domain experts, to understand the decision-making process of a model. However, there are several challenges with current XAI methods: the first challenge is lack of direct quality evaluation metrics as there is no widely accepted metric to quantitatively assess the quality of explanations provided by XAI methods. This makes it difficult to objectively measure how good an explanation is. The second issue is the domain suitability issue since not all XAI methods are appropriate for every domain. Some fields, such as healthcare or finance, may require specialized explanations that current XAI methods don't fully support. The third challenge is related to the developer-centric design. Most XAI tools are developed with AI engineers or data scientists in mind, rather than end-users like healthcare professionals. As a result, the explanations provided by XAI may not be intuitive or useful for non-technical users.

II. Methods and Results

The generalization capability of a CNN model was evaluated by measuring their performance to new subjects, different OR locations, and different procedure types. Moreover, model generalization with respect to the size and variability of training data was also studied in [7].

The evaluation of model robustness to adversaries contains the success rate of misclassification and the size of modification. We proposed a new method called step adaptive iterative fast gradient sign method that can reduce the perturbation of adversaries [4,5]. Particularly, the step size α was controlled by the loss. As shown in figure 1, α

has a consistent changing trend with the loss at each iteration [4,5]. Compared to other step size reduction functions, such as iteration decay, step decay, exponential decay, our loss adaptive decay function could successfully fool the model with less perturbations [4,5].

Figure 1: Modify an image from its original class Grasper to the target class Bipolar using our step-adaptive iterative fast gradient sign method.

To improve the model robustness, we introduced two methods. The first method is adding the conformity loss (1) at shallower layers to help the model to learn a better separated feature space [6]. This conformity loss (1) enforces the features closer to their true classification region and farther from the rest classification regions in the training process. The conformity loss can also be used as evaluation metric on the test set to quantify the feature compactness and inter-class difference; a lower value indicates our model has learned a better feature space. Also, the model robust to PGD attack and FGSM attack was improved [6].

$$L_c(x, y) = \sum_i \frac{2\|f_i - c_i\|_2}{\sum_{j \neq i} (\|f_i - c_j\|_2 + \|c_i - c_j\|_2)} \quad (1)$$

The second method to improve model robustness is adversarial training with borderline samples. The reason of using borderline adversaries for adversarial training is the trade-off problem [8], if the adversarial samples were modified too much, it will reduce the model accuracy on clean data. The preliminary experiments show our borderline adversarial training could gain a relative higher robustness against different attacks while maintain the classification ability on clean data.

For AI certification, to solve the first research problem, Stodt et al. introduced a new metric to evaluate the XAI explanations [9]. The new metrics are named as the Explanation Significance Assessment (ESA) and Weighted Explanation Significance Assessment (WESA) metrics [9]. The proposed ESA metric comprises four components to comprehensively assess the quality of the explanation.

For the second problem, Stodt et al. proposed the optimized FastCAM [10]. The optimized FastCAM weights reflect the reality of the focus for the target domain compared to the original weights. Areas that are important for the recognition are the focus of the model. Focus areas that are not connected to main focus area are distraction area. Unimportant areas are masked. Masked areas that occlude

a part of the instrument are the occlusion areas. The original FastCAM weights showed high occlusion, the optimized approach reduced occlusion and distraction of on average of 24 % compared to state of the art. For the third problem, Stodt et al. established practical guidelines for designing transparent and user-friendly XAI explanations. The guidelines includes nine requirements for assessing the usability of XAI methods [11].

III. Conclusions

In this project, the AI model was evaluated and improved from different aspects. However, although the robustness and verification of AI model were enhanced in statistical level, the unknown weak point of the high-dimensional model structure still challenge the algorithm to give very certain and reliable solutions.

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